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JOB INVOLVEMENT AND WORK MOTIVATION: A STUDY OF MALE AND FEMALE TEACHERS OF CBSE AFFILIATED +2 SCHOOLS WITH REFERENCE TO PATNA, BIHAR

BENKAT KRISHNA BHARTI

UGC- NET

Department of Psychology
Patna University, Patna

Abstract

The present investigation was aimed to see the significance of difference between male and female teachers working in CBSE Affiliated +2 Schools with reference to Patna, Bihar inters of work motivation and job involvement. Total sample consisted of one hundred sixty (N=160) teachers comprising male (n=80) and female (n=80) randomly selected from in and around Patna – a capital of Bihar, India. The subjects' age were ranged between 28 – 52 years. Data were collected through questionnaire schedules of work motivation and job involvement along with self prepared personal information sheet. Having collected the data, data were tabulated according to procedure of the scales. Finally the results indicated that male teachers more or less maintain markedly higher level of work motivation and job involvement, although significance of differences have been found between the group on different dimensions of work motivation. Moreover, significant difference has also been found on the degree of job involvement. In the present study also teachers' motivation and job involvement have found to be positively correlated. Obtained results have been discussed in detail by giving appropriate reasons.

Key Words: Work Motivations, Job Involvement, Male and Female Teachers, Patna.

Introduction:

The concept of job involvement has gained much importance with regard to work environment. Different definitions of job involvement have a common core of meaning in that, they described job involved person as one for whom work is a very important part of life and who is affected by much responsibilities of his whole job satisfaction – the work itself, his co-workers, the company etc. On the other hand, non involved worker does his/her living off the job. Bass (1965) mentioned different conditions that strengthen job involvement of employees such as opportunity to make decision, self determination, recognition and freedom to set one's own work pace.

As we are aware that work has become highly complex phenomenon in this highly modernized technological era where each and every individual employee is trying to compete each other in the productive world. To understand world of work, we need to recognize some facts, and analyze its various components and aspects. As we know that work may be a task, a duty, and / or an accomplishment. It may be mental, physical, or both. Work has not only an economic and mechanical aspect, but it also has a psychological aspects. Regardless of its meaning, work cannot be considered separate from the individual who performs it. Some psychological characteristics of the individual influence his performance to a task.

Job involvement of employees has been reported to varying with their occupational level. Employees who belong to high level have more opportunities to be involved with their job because higher level of the job has greater opportunity to satisfy motivator needs and greater autonomy, challenge and responsibility. Researches done in this area have shown mixed results. Some studies indicate that job involvement increases linearly from workers to chief (Anantharaman and John, 1983; Mishra and Singh, 1986; Singh and Pestonjee, 1990). There is other group of researchers who found no significant results in comparing job involvement and job level (Schuler, 1973; Rao, 1980; Singh, 1987). Some studies indicate that middle managers had more job involvement than higher and lower levels (Das, 1983; Anantharaman and Begum, 1982). Motivational concepts play a major role in most serious efforts to analyze and explain individual's behaviour at work. Motivation is the unifying concept for human and cuts across all principles of organizational psychology.

The concept of job involvement is closely related to motivation. Involvement can result from the fulfillment of motivation and new sources of involvement can generate other motivations. Motivation to work is human state where competence to work and will to work fuse together. In absence of one, the other does not produce results. Kleinback (1987) defines motivation as the direction of attentional effort directed to the task and the content to which attentional effort towards the task is maintained overtime. The latter is important in the work setting because employees are expected to maintain high attendance, good performance and the like as long as they remain with the organization. Mishra (1986) found low work motivation among Indian employees because they do not value work as intrinsically satisfying. Work motivation in organization is not going to improve unless they believe that goodness of work and industry is their moral responsibility leading to job involvement.

Objective of the present study:

It is important to be mentioned here that job involvement and intrinsic work motivation seem to be similar to each other in certain extent but they may not be considered to be the same. However, the distinctness or community and the relationships of the two are still ambiguous. Having reviewed the survey of literature, it has been observed that a large number of researches have been carried out to study the motivation and job involvement of the various cadres of industrial/organizational personnel but the study of teachers' work motivation and job involvement has remained almost neglected. Hence, the present investigation was planned to study the job involvement and work motivation of male and female teachers who are working in CBSE +2 schools in Patna, Bihar. Moreover, the relationship between the two variables will also be examined in the present piece of research work.

Hypotheses:

On the basis of the broad objectives of the present study the following hypotheses were formulated

1. There would be no significant difference between the group of male and female teachers working in CBSE Affiliated +2 Schools on different dimensions of work motivation.
2. Male and female teachers of CBSE Affiliated +2 Schools will not differ on Job Involvement.
3. Job Involvement and Work Motivation of male and female teachers working in CBSE Affiliated +2 Schools would be positively related.

Methodology:

Sample: For the present piece of research work total sample one hundred sixty (N=160) teachers were selected randomly from different CBSE affiliated schools from in and around Patna comprising male (n=80) and female (n=80) teachers. The sample included the teachers teaching various subjects of Arts, Science and Commerce to the classes up to XII. The precautions were taken to keep the two groups of teachers matchable with regard to the

biographical variables such as age, job tenure, salary and the subjects of their teaching, etc. The subjects' age were ranged between 28 – 52 years

Tools Used: The following tools were employed to collect the data for assessing the levels of work motivation and job involvement:

1. **Job Involvement Scale:** For measuring the degree of Job Involvement of the teachers the Hindi adaptation (Kapoor and Singh, 1978) of the Lodahl and Kejner (1965) Job Involvement Scale was used. Scale consisted of 20 items for measuring the phenomena such as indifference, alienation, very high involvement, high sense of duty toward work, tendencies to avoid not coming to work and guilt over unfinished work, pride in the organization, general ambition and upward mobility. The index of split-half reliability of the adopted scale is .73 as reported by the author of the scale.
2. **Employees Motivation Schedule:** For assessing the teachers' various work motivations the Employees Motivation Schedule developed by Shrivastava (1981) was used. The schedule consisted of 70 items to be rated on 4-point scale. The schedule measures the strength of seven needs motivating the employees operating the context of industrial organizations or any other similar organizations. They are; need for personal growth, need for achievement, need for self control, need for monetary gains, need for non-financial gains (such as status, recognition, appreciation, prospects), need for autonomy and self-actualization, and need for social affiliation and conformity. The schedule of split-half reliability of the above mentioned seven sub scales are .82,.79,.74, .77, .81, .72 and .79, respectively.

TABLE: 1

Table: 1 Showing Significance of Difference between Male and Female Teachers Working in CBSE Affiliated +2 Schools in Patna, Bihar on the Dimensions of Work Motivation and Job Involvement

Dimensions of Work Motivation	Male Teachers (n=80)		Female Teachers (n=80)		t - value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Personal Growth	32.10	5.69	32.35	5.06	0.29
Achievement	30.69	5.85	32.49	5.36	2.02*
Self Control	34.39	5.66	30.23	5.73	4.57**
Monetary gain	29.13	6.28	25.89	6.94	3.11**
Non-financial gain	28.32	5.12	27.18	6.59	1.22
Autonomy and self affiliation	30.43	6.07	27.25	5.76	3.38**
Social affiliation	28.25	6.62	28.34	5.83	0.09
Job Involvement	56.27	7.19	53.81	7.15	2.18*

*p .05; **p .01

Results and Discussion:

The obtained results presented in table – 1 clearly points out that male and female teachers working in CBSE affiliated +2 schools significantly differ with regard to their levels on different dimensions of work motivation and job involvement in total. Hence, the proposed hypotheses i.e. there would be no significant difference between the group of male and female teachers working in CBSE Affiliated +2 Schools on different dimensions of work motivation and job involvement in total stand rejected. From the table, it could be well understood that male teachers were found to be comparatively little more motivated especially by their needs for autonomy and self affiliation, monetary, gain and self control. On the other hand female teachers scored higher degree of achievement than their male counterparts. Thus, significance of difference could be observed between the two groups with regard

to their levels of motivation generated by the need for achievement, self control, monetary gain, autonomy and self affiliations. Hence, job involvement have also emerged as the predictor between the group of male and female teachers working in CBSE affiliated +2 schools especially from where the present piece of research work has been carried out.

The results presented above seems to be logical and can be interpreted that in our social system it has been the primary responsibility of the male members of the family to earn bread and butter for its members by taking some job. Though, the female members also have now started sharing this responsibility, and still they consider it as their secondary responsibility. This type of difference prevails in the attitude of male and female teachers might have been instrumental behind the present findings. Since the males have to face more competition in comparison to their female counterpart, hence, they have been observed to be more or less highly motivated by their needs. It is also important to be mentioned that the teachers who trust their own ability to influence their environment, (student group) actually try to influence it more often and more boldly than those who are inclined to let the environment influence them. The present findings coincide with the observation of a good number of previous studies on employees' motivation. Herzberg et al. (1959) have also pointed out that 'money' or 'pay' to be 'hygiene' factor, while the achievement, recognition and advancement were found to be the dominant 'motivators'. Several other researchers have also reported the dominance of psychological and social needs over 'material or physical gain' in motivating the employees (Blum and Russ, 1942; Jurgensen, 1947; Stanger, 1950; Herzberg et al., 1957).

TABLE: 2

Table: 2 Showing Correlation between Dimensions of Work Motivation and Job Involvement of Male and Female Teachers Working in CBSE Affiliated + 2 Schools of Patna, Bihar

Dimensions of Work Motivation	r	
	Male	Female
Personal Growth	.33**	.14
Achievement	.32**	.07
Self Control	.33**	.08
Monetary gain	.27**	.18
Non-financial gain	.17	.27**
Autonomy and self affiliation	.29**	.29**
Social affiliation	.36**	.29**

**p .01

The study also reveals the clear cut picture on the proposed problem that male teachers are more involved in their job as comparison to the female teachers. High job involvement of male teachers may be basically attributed to the causes of their high motivation.

In addition to the above context it can be said that high work motivation of the male teachers, as observed in the study, might have enhanced their job involvement. In the present study male teachers' motivation and job involvement have been found to be positively correlated in all the dimensions except one i.e, non-financial gain (Table- 2). On the other hand, it could be observed from the table that female's teacher group reported to be positively correlated only on non-financial gain, autonomy and self affiliation and social affiliation. The results obtained and discussed on the line of general assumption that the persons highly involved in their job are highly motivated and feel a sense of pride in their work. It is because of the fact that highly motivated employees get involved in their job through their efficient performance as a result of their high level of motivation.

Conclusion:

On the basis of the interpretations of the obtained results the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. Significance of difference between male and female teachers working in CBSE Affiliated +2 Schools have been found on different dimensions of Work Motivation Schedule. They are: “achievement”, “self control”, “monetary gain”, and “autonomy and self affiliation” especially from where the present piece of research work has been carried out.
2. Significance of difference has also been found between the group of male and female teachers on the degree of perceived job involvement.
3. Male teachers’ work motivation and job involvement have been found to be positively correlated except non-financial gain – a one of the important dimensions of work motivation.
4. Female teachers’ work motivation and job involvement have also been found to be positively correlated except “personal growth” achievement”, “self control”, and “monetary gain”. These are the dimensions of work motivation.

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